

ROLE of EMERGING INTERNET of DEVICES in the FIELDS of HEALTH CARE & AGRICULTURE SECTORS and it's APPLICATIONS

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Abstract:

Now a days IODs (internet of devices) have the vital technological improvements when compared to all other technological improvements because of their enormous applications in the field of investigations purpose, space applications, artificially developing new devices and technical enhancements, robotic uses. In this presentation I have adopted the importance of IOD and different IOD enabled sensing devices like heat measuring sensing elements, pressure sensing elements, motion sensors, image sensors, proximity sensors, chemical sensors, optical sensors, infrared sensors, gyroscopic sensors, acceleration sensors, gas and smoke sensing elements, humidity sensing elements etc and their exertions in the fields of finding new holdings and manufacturing purposes due to their various uses.

key words: IOD-internet of devices, artificial intelligence, robotics, image sensors, proximity sensors, chemical sensors, optical sensors, infrared sensors, gyroscopic sensors, acceleration sensors, gas and smoke sensors, humidity sensors.

I. INTRODUCTION

IOD plays vital role in the field of ai developing new things and robotic based activities the investigators can investigate new entities with the help of distinctive sensing elements and IOD^[2]. An is the process of joining distinctive house hold objects and/or distinctive firm equipment or devices and/or research purpose we connect distinctive things through internet sensing devices are used to sense different parameters like temperature humidity gas fire air quality optical rays acceleration images proximity velocity speed time environmental factors present days of network connections^[2] used to connect different devices using wireless-fidelity joining Bluetooth joining etc the objects which are working with the help of group of wires wireless-fidelity are simply called as smart devices like house hold devices like washing machines refrigerators house safety devices printing devices web cameras routers modems speakers desktops fans etc all these devices uses some internet protocol sip^{[1][3]}.

II. NEED of IoD in EMERGING TECHNOLOGIES

Since few years IOT become vital role in the technology and research fields^[3] because of its accuracy, fastness these technologies used in house hold purposes like cook room applications, cars, railway stations, metro stations, bus stands, industries, gas and fire safety in industry, schools, robotic applications, space applications, airplanes, ambulances, fire extinguishers in big show rooms, super markets, automobile industry, medical applications, bioelectronic field, biochemical field, environmental applications, defence applications, missiles, RADARS etc.

The devices which are connected internally so-called Smart devices^{[4][5]}. In the field of agriculture also we use these wired and unwired services related to rains, alert regarding water requirement for growing plants, humidity related information, temperature related information etc

Fig 2: Sensor network

Fig-1 Wired Connections between different devices using Internet or Internet of Devices

III. ARCHITECTURE of IOD (INTERNET OF DEVICES)

Internet of devices have enormous applications and use IOD (Internet of devices) which makes growing very fast^{[4][6]}. We can design different innovative devices with the help of IOD and these designs can be acceptable universally because of its easy implementation, fast response, high throughput. The architecture of IOD describes different layers and its applications. IOD architecture-Fig 3, mainly contains 4 stages, namely 1) information gathering surface 2) information sending surface 3) Information Processing Surface 4) Intelligent Application Surface and management from the below figure it is very clear that connecting different devices i.e IOD contains Sensing surface, Network surface information processing surface, Utilization or Application surface^[6].

Fig-2 Architecture of IOD (Internet of Devices)

A. Recognizing the surface/ information gathering surface

Recognizing surface is the first surface of the IOD Architecture, its main function is to gathering the information from various points^{[7][9]}. This surface contains various sensors and actuators these are kept in the required open places to receive the information regarding temperature, humidity, light, gas, sound and other physical parameters. These devices are connected using wire or unwired communication methods. underlaying technologies the components of the physically recognizing surface mainly involve but are not limited to qr codes sensors, RFIDs, WSAWs and WBANs....

B. *Information sending surface*

IOD(Internet of Devices) use a combination of internet communicate through mobiles satellite and unwired networking using wireless fidelity and enocean for sending information across these networking area Bluetooth and Zig-bee technological developments are employed for short-range message transmission the network surface also known as the transport surface which is important for permitting digitized information to move among all parts of an iod structure it utilizes technologies such as http MQTT and AMQP in such a way to facilitate information sending from one application device to another^{[7][9]}.

C. *data process surface*

It is a surface at which the message will process with the help of IOD (internet of devices).This IOD architecture explaining about crucial parameters like hardware components and software programs these are accountable for gathering investigating and resolving the new things from iod this surface consisting of cloud computing based devices they can transmit message from the physically existing climatic position and make sense of it. it collects the original data receiving from sensing elements and proceeds for next level and which is useful message through cloud technology and big data modules^{[7][8][9]}.

D. *intelligent application surface and management*

An intelligent application surface finds how a computers networking system works and completes the task at this application surface the intelligent surface of iod structure tells us about the interaction bw user and network and also used for downloading the content and sending the data to a required location this layer consists of data used for the customers application and business logic the business logic tells us about the real-world business rules and determines how this application was created saved and changed^{[8][9]}.

IV. ROLE of IOD in the FIELD of AGRICULTURE

IoD (Internet of Devices) can be used in the field of Agriculture to ameliorate quality food, to ameliorate product, to estimate climatic conditions etc. The following 15 are the top most operations of IoD^{[9][10][11]}.

- 1) Green house robotization
- 2) Precision tilling
- 3) Irrigation
- 4) Toxin operation
- 5) Robotics
- 6) Drought covering
- 7) outfit monitoring
- 8) Reduction in operation cost
- 9) Beast monitoring
- 10) climatic conditions covering
- 11) Advanced quality
- 12) Waste reduction
- 13) Remote seeing
- 14) Data gathering
- 15) Prophetic analysis for smart husbandry.

V. ROLE of IoD in the FIELD of HEALTH CARE

Presen days peoples are suffering with health problems due lack of food quality, pollution due to bad climatic conditions, water pollution, Industrial pollution etc, to get out from these situations we can utilize the services of IoD. The following are the top 10 application of IoD in the field of Health care^{[10][11]}.
 1)Implantable Glucose Monitoring System 2)Activities tracking while Cancer Treatment 3)Heart monitoring with information 4)Ingestible sensors 5)Medical altering facility 6) Medication Dispensers 7)Wireless sensors 8)Inhalers with tracking facility 9) Connecting the contact lenses 10)Remote monitoring.

VI. FUTURE SCOPE

There is a enormous future for IOT(IOD) technology due to its ability to communicate with other devices and systems within a short span of time with necessary network connections between various devices with the help of IOT/IOD. Artificial Intelligence is another emerging technology in the field of sensor technology. We can create miracles in the combination of IOT, Sensor technology and AI. AI can take own decisions like human and gives fast and accurate results. Smart or Intelligent sensors (Sensors with AI and IOT) can solve many problems in smart way and provides comfortable or flexible life to human beings. Intelligent sensors are capable to measure temperature, acceleration, angular velocity, time, motion etc. Motion sensors, proximity sensors etc have vast scope in future in saving electricity, energy with low costs.

VII. CONCLUSION

In view of future demands of Internet of Devices, everyone should have a knowledge on Internet of Devices and must learn how to use it through proper practice.

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